

Speculation on the Two-Dimensionality of the Free Particle $\exp(ipx)$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 18, 2022

A classical wave (string, sound, water etc) which satisfies the classical wave equation is described by a “snapshot” profile $\cos(-Et+px)$ at an instant in time. By changing t and x such that $-E dt + p dx = 0$ one follows this translating profile through time and space, but physically a sound, string or water wave is not simply translating like this. The medium fills the “trough” where the wave once passed, but the medium is not part of the wave and so need not be included in its solution. There is a wave profile, but at the same time changes to the profile which are excluded.

In this note we speculate that the form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ used to describe a free quantum particle (and associated with a kind of dynamic probability like the classical wave’s $\cos(-Et+px)$) is two dimensional because it describes both a profile in space due to a kind of momentum-energy wave acting on a single particle, but also as a second dimension the magnitude of the change in this wave $\sin(px)$ unlike the classical wave approach. In other words, for a single particle which is the medium of the energy-momentum wave, it cannot be removed or excluded (hence a particle-wave duality). We suggest there should be a physical mechanism associated with this - in other words the motion of a quantum particle is not a simple translation.

Classical Motion

Classical mechanics seems to treat both classical particles and waves as translating objects. For example, an accelerating particle is seen as moving with a constant $v(x)$ within dx . In the next dx region it has a constant velocity of $v(x) + dv(x)$.

A classical wave is given by the profile $\cos(-Et+px)$ (sound, string, water) so a translational picture follows from: $0 = -E dt + p dx$. Physically this is a solution of a classical wave equation at each x and t , but there are also physical mechanisms occurring due to the changes in space-time as the crest moves along. This somehow does not seem to be captured in the classical picture. It appears to be a snapshot approach because the medium is separated from the energy-momentum wave. Thus one does not really need to focus on how the “water” fills in the wave trough as the crest moves along. Such a scenario, however, does not apply to a single quantum particle which must move along with the energy-momentum wave.

Quantum Mechanical Free Particle

In a previous note (1) we argued that one may write $v=x/t$ in either the relativistic or nonrelativistic free particle action A and vary independently with respect x and t :

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \quad ((1a)) \quad dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad ((1b)) \quad \text{with } A = -Et + px \text{ as a solution}$$

$$\text{Eigenvalue equations are: } -i d/dx \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and } i d/dt \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((2b))$$

Thus x and t seem to be separated. The solution $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is obtained not as a solution of the classical wave equation (which it satisfies if $v = E/p$), but as an eigenfunction of a momentum operator $-i\hbar d/dx$ with $v=p/E$. This suggests, we argue, that momentum flow for a quantum particle is complicated and involves two dimensions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. We have not included $-Et$ because we argue that $\exp(-iEt)$ should be treated separately as it describes an overall energy resonance. For a free particle $E=pp/2m$, but for a bound quantum particle $\exp(-iEnt)$ is “removed” so to speak and one deals with various two dimensional $\exp(ipx)$ in a statistical manner i.e. $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

One may note the similarity of the dimension $\cos(px)$ with the classical wave form $\cos(-Et+px)$, but for the particle there is a second dimension $\sin(px)$ which must be accounted for.

Sin(px) as the Magnitude of Change of exp(ipx)?

We argue that $\sin(px)$ is the magnitude of change of $\cos(px)$ in the next dx interval if one considers changes of $d(px)$. In other words, different energy flows p are associated with different infinitesimal regions $d(px)$ if dx is constant. This is in keeping with the high frequency short wavelength picture of high p $\cos(px)$. In other words, we argue there is first a spatially profile $\cos(px)$ due to an energy-momentum wave acting on a single particle as its medium. The particle’s energy is not spread out over space in a wave form (as Einstein argued in 1905), but rather its probability varies. At the same time the $\cos(px)$ profile is changing in space like a classical wave’s crest which moves along. $\sin(px)$ is the magnitude of this change in the next dx interval. Unlike a classical wave in which the medium (string, gas particles for sound or water) are in a sense separate from the wave, for a single quantum free particle, the particle itself cannot be separated from the energy-momentum wave. Thus changes in the $\cos(px)$ profile are due to changes in the same particle which part of this $\cos(px)$ profile. As a result, there are two dimensions: $\cos(px)$ the wave profile and $\sin(px)$ the magnitude of the change which both are linked to the particle.

Consider $\cos(x)$ and $\sin(x)$ as $x=0$. Here we use x in place of px for simplicity. $\cos(x)=1$ and $\sin(x) = 0$ so it is as if one has a crest at $x=0$. One may ask: how do changes occur?

$\cos(x+dx) (x=0) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} dx dx$ ((3a)) $\sin(dx)=dx$ ((3b)) (to first order) describes the change that occurs in the next interval.

In other words, the quantum free particle picture involves the wave disturbance at x and the magnitude of the change which occurs at $x+dx$.

If one argues that $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of dynamical probability, then it should be conserved. The two pieces $1+.5dxdx$ and dx do not add to 1. If one uses the following rule i.e a dot product magnitude then:

$$(1-.5dxdx)(1-.5dxdx) + dxdx = 1 \quad ((4))$$

Thus the two components of $\exp(ipx)$ add like a vector dot product because the two are orthogonal so to speak.

As a result, because a free particle takes on a probability x profile due to an energy-momentum wave, but also must express the changes to this wave as it moves along there must be two dimensions. Overall probability must be conserved and one is forced to use an $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ approach to finding the overall magnitude of probability.

Bound State Scenario

For a bound single quantum particle one may use a statistical approach i.e. consider an ensemble of free particle $\exp(ipx)$'s such that:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \text{ where } W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

One may then impose conservation of energy at each x point because one uses $V(x)$ and so retains a classical sense of conservation.

$$\text{Thus: } KE \text{ classical } (x) = \{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((6))$$

One may note that each $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional, but if $a(p)=a(-p)$ or if $a(p)=-a(-p)$ then one dimension drops out when one adds $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$. This leaves an average over one dimension which is very similar to the classical wave approach. In other words, $v_{rms}(x)$ is an average of one dimensional wave pieces which are all either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. As a result, $v_{rms}(x)$ is classical and describes a translating object i.e. $v_{rms}(x)$ is a constant within dx just as in the classical case where $v(x)$ is constant within dx . There is no sense of two dimensions from $\exp(ipx)$ acting at the same time. This does not mean that one does not still see the effects of the energy-momentum wave profile i.e. $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. $W(x)$ which is real (i.e. one dimensional). $W(x)$ still has crests and troughs which is quantum mechanical.

Case of Two Dimensions Acting Together

For the bound single particle case we argued that the two dimensionality of $\exp(ipx)$ disappears because only one dimension manifests itself i.e. either $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. For interference scenarios (e.g. two slit interference or interference between two identical particles) it seems that both dimensions come into play i.e.

$$P(x) = | \exp(-ipx) + \exp(-ip(x+b)) | | \exp(ipx) + \exp(ip(x+b)) | \quad ((7)) \ b=\text{constant}$$

Thus the two dimensional features of $\exp(ipx)$ manifest themselves in experiments.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that a classical wave may be described by “one dimension” i.e. $\cos(-Et+px)$ because the medium (water, string, air etc) is separate from the energy-momentum wave i.e. the disturbance in the medium. The disturbance moves along, but the medium is not part of the wave.

For a quantum single particle, this particle is the medium of the energy-momentum wave, but it must move along with the disturbance because there is only one particle. Hence there is a particle wave duality. Furthermore we argue that one may not simply describe a spatial profile $\cos(px)$ like with the classical wave. Two dimensions are needed because one must describe both the profile $\cos(px)$ and the magnitude of its change $\sin(x)$ which occurs with $x+dx$. Thus there two profiles moving along together. These are linked to probability and physical mechanisms we argue, but do not add as scalars, but rather like the dot product of a two dimensional vector. Thus $W^*(x)W(x)$ is used. [One may show formally that if $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ and $P(x/p) = a^*(p)\exp(-ipx)/W^*(x)$ then $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$.]

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Action/Lagrangian Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)